

**THE MEDIATING EFFECT OF VOCABULARY KNOWLEDGE ON THE
LANGUAGE AWARENESS AND READING COMPREHENSION:
A QUANTITATIVE STUDY**

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The Mediating Effect of Vocabulary Knowledge on the Language Awareness and Reading Comprehension: A Quantitative Study

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Abstract

The study aimed to explore the mediating effect of vocabulary knowledge on the language awareness and reading comprehension of English education students in a local college. This study engaged a quantitative method design, utilizing a mediation analysis approach. The participants of the study were the English education students from all year levels. There were 214 students who were randomly selected for quantitative. The data was collected through a survey questionnaire. Based on the results of the study, it was determined that the level of language awareness is moderate, the level of vocabulary knowledge is low, and reading comprehension is low. Furthermore, the mediation analysis of this study revealed that vocabulary knowledge partially mediates the relationship between language awareness and reading comprehension as perceived by English major students. The perceived level of vocabulary knowledge has a positive relationship with the perceived level of reading comprehension. Moreover, in the manner of partial mediation, this stipulates that even without the presence of vocabulary knowledge, there is still a significant relationship between language awareness and reading comprehension as perceived by English major students. The findings of this study highlight the critical role of vocabulary knowledge in mediating the relationship between language awareness and reading comprehension among English education students. The low levels of vocabulary knowledge and reading comprehension observed in the sample suggest that targeted interventions are necessary to address these deficiencies and enhance the overall language proficiency of the students.

Keywords: *language awareness, mediation analysis, reading comprehension, vocabulary knowledge, Philippines*

Introduction

Reading comprehension is defined as the ability to understand the ideas in a text and correctly guess the text's meaning. That is, reading comprehension refers to the ability to read, process, and understand text. An individual's ability to understand text is influenced by their inherent abilities and characteristics, including the ability to draw inferences. Furthermore, reading comprehension can help students develop their writing strategies and vocabulary. When they read a passage, they will be able to draw the information from the written text and interpret the information appropriately. However, in the actual teaching process, many teachers are still not aware of this. Educators face various challenges in teaching reading comprehension, with vocabulary, decoding skills, stamina, and sentence structure being key areas of difficulty, as well as the emphasis on teaching comprehension strategies and the integration of content, skills, and writing in reading instruction, which highlights the complexity of addressing reading comprehension (Mansor, 2017; Sawchuk, 2024).

In the global sector, especially in Malaysia, the most pressing issue is students' reading comprehension. For ESL students from Malaysia who were enrolled in elementary school, reading comprehension is present. Students must deal with a general difficulty understanding narrative texts from books, articles, newspapers, and magazines. This exercise may be difficult for students because of their low reading frequency and comprehension; even though they have received formal instruction in English, most ESL students don't have strong reading habits. When reading a text, students may face a variety of reading comprehension challenges text. There are numerous variables, including the learner's word knowledge, content knowledge, motivation, reading techniques, and reading process. Consequently, this hindrance to reading comprehension extends to active participation in academic contexts, hindering students' ability to contribute effectively to class discussions and express their thoughts coherently (Marashi & Rahmati, 2017; Kaur, 2018).

In the national setting, specifically in Calamba City, reading comprehension emerges as a significant concern, particularly in communities characterized by low literacy levels and living in poverty. Students, navigating multiple difficulties in languages, experience a lack of comprehension variations in reading, primarily due to limited exposure to narrative literature and reading materials during their early childhood. This can be seen as one factor why people with low literacy and a low level of reading comprehension struggle to be successful: the social impact and education context. They have low self-esteem, fear, powerlessness, and a lack of awareness about the contents. People with low levels of reading comprehension are unable to perform well at work or school. As low-level readers cannot

They communicate effectively, but there is a barrier between their interactions with the world. Low-level readers are unable to communicate effectively, which creates a barrier between them and the rest of the world. As a result of these factors, they are unable to perform well at work or in school (Gunn, 2018).

In connection, the researcher had not come across any study that established the students' vocabulary knowledge as mediating the relationship between language Awareness and reading comprehension in the relationship of language awareness and reading comprehension the local context. There is an urgency to conduct this study because it is a worrying phenomenon in English.

Because students' reading comprehension is inadequate, the researcher was unable to find any studies that established students' vocabulary knowledge as having a mediating impact on the relationship between language awareness and reading comprehension in the local setting. There is an urgent need to conduct this study because it is a concerning phenomenon among English students who lack reading comprehension. If neglected or unattended, the students will continue to struggle or perform poorly in reading comprehension. Such a situation could have worsened, which will affect the quality of education in the field of learning. Hence, the relevance of studying this study in our society is very important because it enhances vocabulary and awareness of language, especially the strong comprehension of students and even regular individuals, as this study could help them to comprehend better as they will be able to grasp the meaning conveyed in different texts with fluency.

Moreover, there have been prior studies that are related to this study. One of these studies focuses on and highlights reading comprehension as a complex cognitive activity that is challenging to teach and measure. Moreover, it emphasizes the importance of effective practices in reading instruction. Also explores the scientific aspects of reading comprehension instruction, providing valuable insights into effective teaching methods and strategies (Elleman, 2019; Duke, 2021).

In addition, another study focuses on Different levels of reading comprehension in higher education. offering valuable perspectives on enhancing students' reading skills at an advanced level and discussing the synergistic relationship between word recognition instruction and reading comprehension, emphasizing effective practices for building a strong foundation in reading (Delapenia & Rojas, 2021). However, although they are related, none of these studies focus on or highlight the mediating effect of vocabulary knowledge on language awareness and reading comprehension. Investigating how different vocabulary knowledge interacts with language awareness could provide valuable insights for educators and instructional designers aiming to optimize reading comprehension, ultimately enhancing student engagement and learning outcomes. The result is expected to reveal an insight and understanding of the mediating effect of vocabulary knowledge on Language awareness and reading comprehension among English majors. The research findings of this study will be shared with relevant stakeholders, partners, academic institutions, and community members by sharing copies of research papers, reports, or summaries. The purpose of this dissemination strategy is to make it available to key stakeholders so that they can actively participate in understanding important research findings. The researcher hopes to increase the importance and relevance of the research in scientific, collaborative, academic, and community contexts by disseminating paper versions of the research article.

Research Objectives

The goal of this research was to determine the mediating effect of vocabulary knowledge on language awareness and reading comprehension of Bachelor of Secondary Education major in English students. To be specific, this study explored to reveal the following objectives:

1. To determine the level of Vocabulary knowledge in terms of:
 - 1.1. vocabulary form;
 - 1.2. vocabulary meaning; and,
 - 1.3. vocabulary use.
2. To determine the level of language awareness in terms of
 - 2.1. affective domain;
 - 2.2. social domain;
 - 2.3. power domain;
 - 2.4. cognitive domain; and,
 - 2.5. performance domain.
3. To determine the level of reading comprehension in terms of:
 - 3.1. literal comprehension;
 - 3.2. interpretive comprehension;
 - 3.3. evaluative comprehension; and,
 - 3.4. creative comprehension.
4. To determine the significant relationship between the following:
 - 4.1. language awareness and reading comprehension
 - 4.2. language awareness and vocabulary knowledge; and
 - 4.3. vocabulary knowledge and reading comprehension.
5. To determine the mediating impact of vocabulary knowledge on language awareness and reading comprehension among English majors.

Methodology

Research Design

This study used quantitative research since the quantitative research design is a systematic approach that focuses on data collection and analysis that relies on numerical data and statistical methods. It also seeks to understand, describe, or explain phenomena by measuring

and quantifying variables, often using structured surveys or experiments. This research method emphasizes objectivity, replicability, and the use of statistical analysis to draw conclusions and identify patterns and relationships in the data. It is commonly used in various fields to generalize findings, test hypotheses, and make data-driven inferences (Coghlan & Brydon-Miller, 2014).

This study is quantitative since it will quantify variables or test varying interventions through correlational and mediation analysis. The primary purpose of this research study is to investigate the connection between the vocabulary knowledge and language awareness and its impact on the reading comprehension of students. Which will be undergo by hypothesis, gathering data using surveys and observations and through statistical analyses, including correlation and regression in a specific educational setting, which will analyze the relationships between different variables. The outcomes of this research have the potential to provide valuable insights and improve teaching practices, ultimately leading to a better quality of education.

A descriptive-correlational research design aims to explain the relationship between two or more variables without making any causal claims. It entails gathering and analyzing data from at least two variables to determine whether they are related. Additionally, data collection helps researchers better understand the variables of interest and their interactions. Without changing the variables or presuming that one thing affects another, the main objective is to give a comprehensive description of the variables and their interactions. Descriptive correlational study designs measure the magnitude and direction of the relationship between two or more variables in order to reveal their associations. Initially established equivalence among the groups or variables (Miksza et al., 2023).

Descriptive-correlational research design is considered in this study because it allows us to gain a deeper understanding of vocabulary knowledge's mediation role in pupils' language awareness and reading comprehension. The primary goal of this study is to provide an overview of these variables and identify any potential connections between them. To achieve this, this study will gather data through surveys, observations, and data analysis. By doing this, it will be easier to see how the students' language awareness and reading comprehension in our classroom are impacted by common patterns in vocabulary knowledge. Additionally, it will also explore potential correlations between these two variables. This will help us gain a more thorough understanding of vocabulary knowledge and its potential impact on students' language awareness and reading comprehension. However, it is important to note that our research does not aim to establish causation, but rather to provide valuable insights into the dynamics of the classroom.

Mediation analysis in quantitative research examines the process through which one variable influence another by exploring the role of an intermediate variable. It helps to understand the mechanism or pathway of the relationship between the independent and dependent variables. The analysis typically involves testing three relationships: the effect of the independent variable on the mediator, the effect of the mediator on the dependent variable, and the direct effect of the independent variable on the dependent variable (MacKinnon et al., 2007).

In the study, mediating analysis serves as a crucial statistical method. By applying mediation, in the context of studying the Vocabulary knowledge's mediating effect on language awareness and reading comprehension would be investigated using mediation analysis. The analysis helps unveil the potential pathway through which language awareness impacts reading comprehension, shedding light on the importance of vocabulary knowledge as an intermediary factor in this relationship.

Respondents

This study involved Bachelor of Secondary Education students major in English enrolled at Kapalong College of Agriculture, Science, and Technology for the academic year 2023-2024. The respondents in the study were primarily drawn from this institution using the Slovin's formula with a margin of error of 0.05. Out of the total population of 457 students, 214 students were chosen as respondents. To ensure a representative sample, the researchers employed stratified random sampling with proportional Table 1 presents the distribution of the population for this study, highlighting the systematic approach taken to respondents.

Table 1. *Distribution of Respondents*

<i>BSEd English</i>	<i>Population</i>	<i>Sample</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
First Year	223	104	22.85%
Second Year	136	64	13.94%
Third Year	69	32	7.07%
Fourth Year	29	14	2.97%
Total	457	214	46.83%

Instrument

The study adopted three downloadable sources of indicators, which the researcher used to create a researcher-made questionnaire to measure the variables. The instrument for vocabulary knowledge was adopted based on the study of Tong-Qing (2017). The instrument is composed of 30 items on a researcher-made questionnaire, a multiple-choice type of questionnaire. In addition, the language awareness researcher-made questionnaire was adopted based on the study of Audriyan et al. (2021). The language awareness questionnaire is in the form of descriptive data analysis, has a 5-point Likert-type scale, and was measured by 25 items.

Moreover, the instrument for reading comprehension was adopted based on the study of Bilbao et al. (2016). The instrument is composed of 40 items on a researcher-made questionnaire, a multiple-choice type of questionnaire.

Procedure

To obtain authorization to carry out the research, the investigator looked for the school President of Kapalong College of Agriculture, Sciences, and Technology granted permission to conduct the study and collect data on the school's total population of BSEd-English students. When gathering the data, the researcher observed the following:

Crafting of Questions. The researcher made a question that helped the achievement of the research objectives. It was presented to her adviser for comments, corrections, and suggestions.

Submission and Revision of Questionnaires for Validation. After the modification of questionnaires this was submitted to the panel of experts for validations and corrections Upon receiving feedback and connection the researcher revised the questionnaires which made them more effective in applying the suggestions of the panel.

Distribution And Retrieval of the Questionnaires. After Following approval, the researcher personally distributed the research instrument to the respondents and carried out the study. The administration and teachers worked together to ensure that all questionnaires were distributed and retrieved correctly.

Collection and Tabulation of Data. At this point, the research instrument was retrieved and tabulated. The researchers found it convenient to conduct the study on the students of Kapalong College of Agriculture, Sciences and Technology.

Data Analysis

The data was calculated using the following statistical techniques, and the hypothesis was tested at the 0.05 level of significance.

Mean. This statistical tool was used to determine the levels of parental involvement, self-efficacy, and reading skills.

Pearson-r. The association between vocabulary knowledge, language awareness, and reading comprehension was ascertained using this statistical method for all English majors.

Multiple regression. This was used to identify the domains of vocabulary knowledge that influence language awareness and reading comprehension.

Results and Discussion

The main conclusions and outcomes of the study examining the mediating role of vocabulary knowledge on the connection between language awareness and reading comprehension among BSED-English students are presented in this chapter. The data were analyzed and interpreted in a way that was consistent with the goals of the study. The study looked at the theory that the relationship between language awareness and reading comprehension is mediated by vocabulary knowledge. The findings show an indirect effect, mediating effect, and positive connection.

Level of language awareness in terms of affective Domain

The level of language awareness in terms of affective domain is presented, analyze, and interpreted. Reflected in Table 2 is the level of Language awareness in terms of affective domain of English major students with means ranging from 2.70 to 3.40 with a corresponding overall mean of 2.74 or qualitatively interpreted as moderate. It could be observed from the data that the Item no. 5-

Table 2. *Level of Language Awareness in terms of Affective Domain*

	<i>Affective Domain</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
1.	Learning the English language better when I find it valuable to my studies.	2.51	Low
2.	Eagerly learning the English language when I am motivated.	2.76	Moderate
3.	Exploring the forms and functions of the English language when I am curious about it.	2.60	Low
4.	Finding learning the English language easier if I can relate it to real-life situations.	2.81	Moderate
5.	Finding the English language useful and important for communication inside and outside the school.	3.02	Moderate
Overall mean		2.74	Moderate

Finding the English language useful and important for communication inside and outside the school. Contains the highest mean rating of 3.02, or moderate, which means that language awareness in terms of the affective domain is sometimes manifested. As opposed to this, Item no. 1- Learning the English language better when I find it valuable to my studies. Contains the lowest mean rating of 2.51, or low, means that language awareness in terms of the affective domain is seldom manifested.

The Level of Language Awareness in terms of Social Domain

The level of language awareness in terms of Social Domain is presented, analyzed, and interpreted. Table 3 displays the degree of linguistic awareness in major students' social domain scores ranging from 2.70 to 3.40 with a corresponding overall mean of 2.86 or qualitatively interpreted as moderate or interpreted as the level of language awareness in terms of social domain in BSEd-English is sometimes manifested.

Table 3. *Level of Language Awareness in terms of Social Domain*

<i>Social Domain</i>		<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
1.	Determining what form of language to use in different contexts or settings.	2.75	Moderate
2.	Communicating well with people with different cultures and behaviors.	2.75	Moderate
3.	Adapting to how the language is used in the society.	2.65	Moderate
4.	Knowing what manner of speaking to be used when having conversation with different people.	3.17	Moderate
5.	Managing to have a meaningful and enjoyable conversation with other people.	2.86	Moderate
Overall mean		2.86	Moderate

It could be observed that the highest mean rating is 3.17, or moderate, and it is found in Item No. 4- Knowing what manner of speaking to be used when having a conversation with different people, which means that language awareness in terms of the social domain is sometimes manifested. As opposed to this, the lowest mean rating of 2.65, or moderate, was found in Item No. 1- Learning the English language better when I find it valuable to my studies, which means that language awareness in terms of social domain is sometimes manifested.

The Level of Language awareness in terms of Power Domain

The level of language awareness in terms of Power Domain is presented, analyze, and interpreted. With averages ranging from 2.70 to 3.40, Table 4 shows the language awareness level of English major students in terms of power domain. with a corresponding overall mean of 3.15 or qualitatively interpreted as moderate or interpreted as the level of language awareness in terms of social domain in BSEd- English is sometimes manifested.

Table 4. *Level of Language Awareness in terms of Power Domain*

<i>Power Domain</i>		<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
1.	Understanding the meaning of spoken or written language used by others.	3.26	Moderate
2.	Understanding what is being said to me even in a figurative sense.	3.29	Moderate
3.	Identifying hidden meanings within texts I read or hear.	2.85	Moderate
4.	Making assumptions of what is being told to me after I hear or read it.	3.13	Moderate
5.	Knowing that language meanings and usage are influenced by societal norms.	3.21	Moderate
Overall mean		3.15	Moderate

It could be observed that the highest mean rating is 3.29, or moderate, and it is found in Item No. 5- Understanding what is being said to me even in a figurative sense, which means that language awareness in terms of the power domain is sometimes manifested. As opposed to this, the lowest mean rating of 3.13, or moderate, was found in Item No. 3- Identifying hidden meanings within texts I read and hear, which means that language awareness in terms of power domain is sometimes manifested.

Level of Language Awareness in terms of Cognitive Domain

The level of language awareness in terms of cognitive Domain is presented, analyzed, and interpreted. Table 5 shows the cognitive domain language awareness of English major students, with averages ranging from 2.70 to 3.40. with a corresponding overall mean of 3.21 or qualitatively interpreted as moderate or interpreted as the level of language awareness in terms of social domain in BSEd- English is sometimes manifested.

Table 5. *Level of Language Awareness in terms of Cognitive Domain*

<i>Cognitive Domain</i>		<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
1.	Considering proper words to use in a situation or conversation.	2.93	Moderate
2.	Recognizing my mistakes in grammar, form and structure while having a conversation.	3.33	Moderate
3.	Correcting my mistakes in grammar, form and structure while writing or talking.	3.29	Moderate
4.	Learning new words from my peers or instructors.	3.52	High
5.	Recognizing the different parts of speech in English.	2.99	Moderate
Overall mean		3.21	Moderate

It could be observed that the highest mean rating is 3.52, or high, and it is found in Item No. 5- Learning new words from my peers or instructors, which means that language awareness in terms of the cognitive domain is oftentimes manifested. As opposed to this, the lowest mean rating of 2.93, or moderate, was found in Item No. 1- Considering proper words to use in a situation or conversation, which means that language awareness in terms of cognitive domain is sometimes manifested.

Level of Language awareness in terms of Performance Domain

The level of language awareness in terms of performance domain is presented, analyzed, and interpreted. Reflected in Table 6 is the level of language awareness in terms of performance domain of English major students with means ranging from 2.70 to 3.40 with a corresponding overall mean of 3.18 or qualitatively interpreted as moderate or interpreted as the level of language awareness in terms of social domain in BSEd-English is sometimes manifested.

It could be observed that the highest mean rating is 3.35, or moderate, and it is found in Item No. 4- Sharing my thoughts and ideas

during class discussion, which means that language awareness in terms of the performance domain is sometimes manifested. As opposed to this, the lowest mean rating of 3.10, or moderate, were found in Item No. 1- Communicating well with others using the English language and Item No. 2- Speaking what I intended to say in using the English language, which means that language awareness in terms of performance domain is sometimes manifested.

Table 6. *Level of Language Awareness in terms of Performance Domain*

<i>Performance Domain</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
1. Communicating well with others using the English language.	3.10	Moderate
2. Speaking what I intend to say using the English language.	3.10	Moderate
3. Delivering information effectively in class reporting using the English language.	3.15	Moderate
4. Sharing my thoughts and ideas during class discussion using English language.	3.35	Moderate
5. Conveying my message clearly to people I am having conversation with using the English language.	2.19	Moderate
Overall mean	3.18	Moderate

Summary on the Level of Language Awareness

The summary on the level of language awareness among English major students is presented, analyzed, and interpreted. The summary of the data on the summary level of language awareness among English major students in the institute towards the language awareness is shown in Table 7 with the means ranging from 2.70 to 3.40 with an overall average mean of 3.03 or qualitatively interpreted as moderate, which means that the level of language awareness in BSEd-English students is sometimes manifested.

The data show that the indicator with the highest average mean rating of 3.21 or moderate is the cognitive domain, which means that the level of language awareness in terms of the cognitive domain is sometimes manifested. As opposed to this, the indicator with the lowest average mean rating of 2.74 or moderate is an affective domain, which means that the level of language awareness in terms of the affective domain is sometimes manifested. With that, the summary of results stipulates that language awareness among English major students is satisfactory, with that, the data analysis of language awareness among English major students reveals an overall moderate average mean of 3.03, with the cognitive domain scoring the highest at 3.21 and lowest the affective domain at 2.74, wherein it this suggests satisfactory language awareness among students, indicating their motivation and engagement in the language.

Table 7. *Summary on the Level of Language Awareness*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Average</i>	<i>Description</i>
Affective Domain	2.74	Moderate
Social Domain	2.86	Moderate
Power Domain	3.15	Moderate
Cognitive Domain	3.21	Moderate
Performance Domain	3.18	Moderate
Total	3.03	Moderate

Summary of the Level of Reading Comprehension

It was presented in Table 8 that the level of reading comprehension among BSEd-English at Kapalong College of Agriculture, Sciences, and Technology obtained an overall mean of 14.33 with a description of low, which means that the level of reading comprehension among BSEd-English is oftentimes manifested.

Table 8. *Summary on the Level of Reading Comprehension*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>	<i>Overall Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
A. Literal Comprehension				
0	10	4.67 %	3.66	Low
1	20	9.35%		
2	44	20.56%		
3	45	21.03%		
4	18	8.41%		
5	34	15.89%		
6	20	9.35%		
7	5	2.34%		
8	18	8.41%		
Total	214	100%		
B. Interpretive Comprehension				
0	12	5.61%	3.52	Low
1	21	9.81%		
2	40	18.69%		
3	50	23.36%		
4	22	10.28%		
5	29	13.55%		

6	23	10.75%		
7	4	1.87%		
8	13	6.08%		
Total	214	100%		
C. Creative Comprehension				
0	7	3.27 %	3.44	Low
1	31	14.49%		
2	45	21.03%		
3	42	19.63%		
4	23	10.75%		
5	32	14.95%		
6	16	7.48%		
7	5	2.34%		
8	12	5.61%		
10	1	0.47%		
Total	214	100%		
D. Evaluative Comprehension				
0	7	3.27%	3.70	Low
1	17	7.94%		
2	35	16.36%		
3	53	24.77%		
4	34	15.89%		
5	30	14.02%		
6	20	9.35%		
7	4	1.87%		
8	14	6.54%		
Total	214	100%		
Total	214	100%	14.33	Low

It could be observed from the data that the level of reading comprehension in terms of literal comprehension The overall mean was 3.66, which is low, indicating that the level of reading comprehension in terms of literal comprehension is oftentimes manifested. Moreover, the level of reading comprehension in terms of interpretive comprehension obtained an overall mean of 3.52, indicating that the level of reading comprehension in terms of interpretive comprehension is frequently demonstrated.

Furthermore, the level of reading comprehension in terms of creative comprehension received an overall mean of 3.44, this was considered low, suggesting that the reading comprehension level in terms of creative comprehension is oftentimes manifested. In alignment with that, the level of reading comprehension in terms of evaluative comprehension obtained an overall mean of 3.70, which was interpreted as low, indicating that the level of reading comprehension in terms of evaluative comprehension is frequently manifested. Thus, Evaluative comprehension, which has a low overall mean of 3.70, is the indication with the greatest overall mean.

Summary of the Levels of Vocabulary Knowledge

It was presented in Table 9 that the level of vocabulary knowledge among BSEd-English at Kapalong College of Agriculture, Sciences, and Technology obtained an overall mean of 13.28 with a description of low, which means that the level of vocabulary knowledge among BSEd-English is oftentimes manifested.

Table 9. Summary on the Level of Vocabulary Knowledge

Indicators	Frequency	Percentage	Overall Mean	Description
Vocabulary Meaning				
0	2	0.94 %	4.43	Low
1	12	5.61%		
2	22	10.28%		
3	29	13.55%		
4	45	21.03%		
5	46	21.50%		
6	29	13.55%		
7	11	5.14%		
8	17	7.94%		
9	1	0.47%		
Total	214	100%		
Vocabulary Use				
0	1	0.47%	4.59	Moderate
1	6	2.80%		
2	17	7.94%		
3	34	15.89%		

4	46	21.50%		
5	40	18.69%		
6	45	21.03%		
7	13	6.08%		
8	12	5.61%		
Total	214	100%		
Vocabulary Form				
0	1	0.47 %	4.20	Low
1	15	7.01%		
2	26	12.15%		
3	40	18.69%		
4	38	17.76%		
5	39	18.22%		
6	30	14.02%		
7	15	7.01%		
8	10	4.67%		
Total	214	100%	13.28	Low

It could be observed from the data that the level of vocabulary knowledge in terms of vocabulary meaning got an overall mean of 4.43, or low, which means that the level of vocabulary knowledge in terms of vocabulary meaning is oftentimes manifested. Moreover, the level of vocabulary knowledge in terms of vocabulary use obtained an overall mean of 4.59, indicating that the degree of word usage frequently reflects the level of vocabulary knowledge.

Additionally, the degree of vocabulary understanding in terms of vocabulary form was frequently demonstrated by the overall mean of 4.20, which was viewed as low. Vocabulary use, which has an overall mean of 4.59 and is regarded as low, is the indication with the highest overall mean. On the other hand, vocabulary form was the indicator with the lowest overall mean, with an overall mean of 4.20, which is considered low.

Significant Relationship Between Language Awareness and Reading Comprehension

Presented in Table 10 was the result of the significant relationship between language awareness and reading comprehension, r -value = .184, $p < .007$. Therefore, The null hypothesis, stating that there is no significant relationship between language awareness and reading comprehension, is rejected in this context. This indicates a moderately positive relationship between language awareness and reading comprehension.

Table 10. *Significant Relationship Between Language Awareness and Reading Comprehension*

Variable	Mean	R-Value	P-Value	Decision @ = 0.05
Language Awareness	3.03			
Reading Comprehension	14.33	.184	.007	Ho Rejected

Significant Relationship Between Language Awareness and Vocabulary Knowledge

Table 11 shows the result of the significant relationship between language awareness and vocabulary knowledge, R -value = .233, $p < .001$. Therefore, the null hypothesis, which states that there is no significant relationship between language awareness and reading comprehension, is rejected in this case. This indicates that there is a moderately positive relationship between language awareness and vocabulary knowledge.

Table 11. *Significant Relationship Between Language Awareness and Vocabulary Knowledge*

Variable	Mean	R-Value	P-Value	Decision @ = 0.05
Language Awareness	3.03			
Vocabulary Knowledge	13.28	.233	<.001	Ho Rejected

Significant Relationship Between Vocabulary Knowledge and Reading Comprehension

Presented in Table 12 was the study found a significant correlation (R -value = .718, $p < .001$) between vocabulary knowledge and reading comprehension. As a result, the null hypothesis, stating that there is no significant relationship between language awareness and reading comprehension, is rejected in this context. This suggests that reading comprehension and word knowledge have a somewhat beneficial association.

Table 12. *Significant Relationship Between Vocabulary Knowledge and Reading Comprehension*

Variable	Mean	R-Value	P-Value	Decision @ = 0.05
Vocabulary Knowledge	13.28			
Reading Comprehension	14.33	.718	<.001	Ho Rejected

Mediating Effect of Vocabulary Knowledge on Language Awareness and Reading Comprehension among English Major Mediation Analysis

The approach used in mediation analysis is based on Preacher and Hayes, who focused on the indirect effect. In this approach, two types of mediation are considered: partial mediation and full mediation. According to partial mediation, indirect and direct effects from X to Y are expected to be significant. Because of this, the unmediated relationship is just as important as the mediator-to-Y and X-to-mediator ties. In full mediation, the mediator does not need to be present for X to have a large direct impact on Y. The direct effect becomes minimal in the presence of the mediator, but the indirect effect becomes significant. Otherwise, the mediation process will not occur if there are negligible relationships between the mediator and X or the mediator and Y. Table 13 shows that language awareness (IV) has an indirect effect on vocabulary knowledge (MV) and reading comprehension (DV). The findings showed that the association between language awareness and reading comprehension was somewhat mediated by vocabulary knowledge ($B=0.385$, $SE=0.113$, 95% confidence interval [0.164, 0.606]), and direct effects from X to Y are expected to be significant. Because the X to the mediator and mediator-to-Y interactions are important, the unmediated relationship is also important. In full mediation, the mediator does not need to be present for X to have a large direct impact on Y.

Table 13. *Indirect Effects*

				Estimate	Std. Error	z-value	p	95% Confidence Interval		
								Lower	Upper	
Language Awareness	→	Vocabulary Knowledge	→	Reading Comprehension	0.385	0.113	3.408	<.001	0.164	0.606

The direct effect becomes minimal in the presence of the mediator, but the indirect effect becomes significant. Otherwise, the mediation process will not occur if there are negligible relationships between the mediator and X or the mediator and Y. Furthermore, Table 14 shows that language awareness has a direct effect on reading comprehension. An estimate of 0.041 and a standard error of 0.113 are obtained from the findings, with $p < 0.715$ signifying significance.

In addition, it can be observed that in every increase in unit language awareness will entice a 0.041 increase in reading comprehension. The results revealed that language awareness is significantly influencing reading comprehension. This indicates that language awareness has a direct effect on reading comprehension. Hence, as the language awareness increase so does reading comprehension.

Consequently, the results indicate that a one-unit rise in the independent variable will lead to a 0.426 increase in the dependent variable. This indicates that the dependent variable's entice value of 0.426 rises. This indicates that reading comprehension, the dependent variable, is significantly impacted by the independent variable.

Table 14. *Direct Effects*

				Estimate	Std. Error	z-value	p	95% Confidence Interval	
								Lower	Upper
Language Awareness	→	Reading Comprehension		0.041	0.113	0.366	0.715	-0.180	0.263

Furthermore, Table 15 revealed that language awareness significantly influenced reading comprehension, $\beta=.041$, $p=.715$. Also, language awareness significantly affected vocabulary knowledge, $\beta=.394$, $p<.001$. Lastly, vocabulary knowledge is found to be a significant predictor of reading comprehension, $\beta=.977$, $p<.001$. This implies the total effect of the relationship among language awareness and reading comprehension

Table 15. *Total Effects*

				Estimate	Std. Error	z-value	p	95% Confidence Interval	
								Lower	Upper
Language Awareness	→	Reading Comprehension		0.426	0.155	2.743	0.006	0.122	0.731

Table 16. *Path Coefficients*

				Estimate	Std. Error	z-value	p	95% Confidence Interval	
								Lower	Upper
Vocabulary Knowledge	→	Reading Comprehension		0.977	0.067	14.606	<.001	0.846	1.108
Language Awareness	→	Reading Comprehension		0.041	0.113	0.366	0.715	0.180	0.263
Language Awareness	→	Vocabulary Knowledge		0.394	0.112	3.505	<.001	0.174	0.614

In addition to the result of the study, the model in Figure 1 demonstrated correlations between language awareness and reading comprehension via the mediating effects of vocabulary knowledge. Path A shows a significant relationship between language awareness (IV) and reading comprehension ($p < 0.39$). Path B revealed a significant correlation ($p < .098$) between language exposure and language awareness.

In Path C, affective learning outcomes was positively predictive of language awareness ($p < 0.04$). These results suggested that the relationship between language awareness and reading comprehension was partly mediated by the indirect pathway through vocabulary knowledge, a claim that was also supported in Table 12 by the estimation of a significant indirect effect.

Figure 1. Path Analysis Showing the Variables of the Study

Furthermore, the result implies that reading comprehension, it should not be limited solely to students' language proficiency. Teachers should investigate other factors influencing a student's reading comprehension, in addition to language awareness. Teachers should also consider student engagement, specifically cognitive, emotional, social, and behavioral engagement, as it partially or significantly influences the relationship between language awareness and reading comprehension.

Conclusions

The recommendations focus on targeted strategies that directly respond to the challenges, offering practical solutions and steps to enhance performance and mitigate obstacles. By implementing these measures, the study anticipates improvements in the relevant areas, contributing to a more efficient and successful outcome.

The study found that English major students at Kapalong College of Agriculture, Sciences, and Technology had a low level of reading comprehension. To build upon these findings, it is recommended that the institution implement strategies to further enhance and cultivate students' reading comprehension skills. This can be achieved by incorporating engaging and interactive learning activities that promote reading comprehension, such as providing opportunities for students to set goals, make choices, and reflect on their learning progress. Teachers may also play a crucial role in supporting students' reading comprehension by assigning daily readings that align with their courses and encourage independent thinking and regulation. By fostering a classroom environment that values reading comprehension, both the institution and Teachers can help students take control of their learning and develop lifelong skills for successful language learning.

In addition, this study indicates that English major students demonstrated a low level of vocabulary knowledge. To dwell on these findings, integrating strategies that could enhance these are essential. Incorporating interactive recitation and daily readings could help these findings. Moreover, the support of teachers and institutions will play a crucial role. So, commitment is necessary.

Also, students majoring in English exhibit a modest level of linguistic awareness, according to this study. To enhance the findings, students should be more exposed to language exercises that will contribute to enhancing their language awareness. Incorporating such methods or techniques like using alternative language or integrating code-switching in the classroom could help them explore the sense of how vital languages are.

Finally, it is recommended that future researchers investigate another variable that could fully mediate the relationship between language awareness and reading comprehension. They are also recommended to utilize other methodologies and factors or variables that the study was not able to cover or might replicate the study in other programs..

References

Afzal, N. (2019). A study on Vocabulary-Learning Problems Encountered by BA English Majors at the university level of education.

Arab World English Journal, 10(3), 81–98. <https://doi.org/10.24093/awej/vol10no3.6>

Ahmadi, M. R., Ismail, H. N., & Kabilan, M. K. (2013). The importance of Metacognitive Reading Strategy Awareness in reading comprehension. *English Language Teaching*, 6(10). <https://doi.org/10.5539/elt.v6n10p235>

Azhar, I., & Rohmah, N. (2021). The comparison of students' academic achievement taught using jigsaw versus demonstration on students' different Self-Confidence. *Darajat Jurnal Pendidikan Agama Islam*, 4(1), 47–62. <https://doi.org/10.58518/darajat.v4i1.645>

Borleffs, E., Maassen, B., Lyytinen, H., & Zwarts, F. (2019). Cracking the code: The Impact of Orthographic Transparency and Morphological-Syllabic Complexity on reading and Developmental Dyslexia. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 9. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2018.02534>

Carter, R. (2003). Language awareness. *ELT Journal*, 57(1), 64–65. <https://doi.org/10.1093/elt/57.1.64>

Coghlan, D., & Brydon-Miller, M. (2014). The SAGE Encyclopedia of Action Research. In SAGE Publications Ltd eBooks. <https://doi.org/10.4135/9781446294406>

Cohen-Azaria, Y. (2022). Kindergarten teachers' evaluation: perceptions of the new Israeli multiple domains performance tool. *Quality Assurance in Education*, 30(2), 184–198. <https://doi.org/10.1108/qa-04-2021-0059>

College Quarterly - Articles - The affective Domain: Undiscovered country. (n.d.). <http://www.senecac.on.ca/quarterly/2007-vol10-num04-fall/pierre-oughton.html>

Duff, D., Tomblin, J. B., & Catts, H. W. (2015). The influence of reading on vocabulary growth: A case for a Matthew effect. *Journal of Speech, Language, and Hearing Research*, 58(3), 853–864. https://doi.org/10.1044/2015_jslhr-1-13-0310

Duff, F. J., Fieldsend, E., Bowyer-Crane, C., Hulme, C., Smith, G., Gibbs, S., & Snowling, M. J. (2008). Reading with vocabulary intervention: evaluation of an instruction for children with poor response to reading intervention. *Journal of Research in Reading*, 31(3), 319–336. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-9817.2008.00376.x>

Education and power. (n.d.). Google Books. https://books.google.com.ph/books?hl=tl&lr=&id=4pLHBQAAQBAJ&oi=fnd&pg=PT6&dq=power+skill+in+education&ots=O3dx70sPOZ&sig=GrJSgjX43YAavGpY6DSdh_sRGZ0&redir_esc=y#v=onepage&q=power%20skill%20in%20education&f=false

Finkbeiner, C., & White, J. (2015). Language Awareness and Multilingualism: A Historical Overview. In Springer eBooks (pp. 1–14). https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-02325-0_1-1Form-focused Instruction in Second Language Vocabulary Learning: A Case for Contrastive Analysis and Translation (A Conceptual Replication Study). (2022). *MEXTESOL Journal*, Vol. 46(No. 3, 2022).

Guthrie, J. T., Wigfield, A., Barbosa, P., Perencevich, K. C., Taboada, A., Davis, M. H., Scaffiddi, N. T., & Tonks, S. M. (2004). Increasing reading Comprehension and engagement through Concept-Oriented Reading instruction. *Journal of Educational Psychology*, 96(3), 403–423. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0022-0663.96.3.403>

Hambrick, D. Z., & Engle, R. W. (2002). Effects of domain knowledge, working memory capacity, and age on cognitive performance: An investigation of the Knowledge-Is-Power hypothesis. *Cognitive Psychology*, 44(4), 339–387. <https://doi.org/10.1006/cogp.2001.0769>

Harackiewicz, J. M., Smith, J. L., & Priniski, S. J. (2016). Interest matters. *Policy Insights From the Behavioral and Brain Sciences*, 3(2), 220–227. <https://doi.org/10.1177/2372732216655542>

Huang, C., & Wang, K. (2019). Comparative analysis of different creativity tests for the prediction of students' scientific creativity. *Creativity Research Journal*, 31(4), 443–447. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10400419.2019.1684116>

Itten-Gee, R., & Manchanda, S. (2021). Using social domain theory to seek critical consciousness with young children. *Theory and Research in Education*, 19(3), 235–260. <https://doi.org/10.1177/14778785211057485> Khemanuwong, T., Angsuwatanakul, T., Phairot, E., Jaritjpaibul, D., Promsuwan, P., & Uampittaya, P. (2021). Reading Comprehension proficiency of English major students. *Asian Conference on Education & International Development Official Conference Proceedings*. <https://doi.org/10.22492/issn.2189-101x.2021.4>

Integrating Children's literature through the Common Core State Standards : Aligned with the Common Core. (n.d.). ND L Search. <https://cir.nii.ac.jp/crid/1130000795285292928>

Kessler, B., Pollo, T. C., Treiman, R., & Cardoso-Martins, C. (2012). Frequency analyses of prephonological spellings as predictors of success in conventional spelling. *Journal of Learning Disabilities*, 46(3), 252–259. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0022219412449440>

{{ Knowledge How }}. (2022). {Pavese, Carlotta}. <https://plato.stanford.edu/archives/fall2022/entries/knowledge-how/>

Krathwohl, D. R. (1964). Taxonomy of educational objectives: the classification of educational goals: handbook II : affective domain /. <http://eduq.info/xmlui/handle/11515/11943>

- Kuo, Y., Batool, S., Devi, S. a. J. S., Tahir, T., & Yu, J. H. (2024). Exploring the impact of emotionalized learning experiences on the affective domain: A comprehensive analysis. *Heliyon*, 10(1), e23263. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2023.e23263>
- Lei, Y., & Reynolds, B. L. (2022). Learning English vocabulary from word cards: A research synthesis. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 13. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2022.984211>
- Leonard, J. (2018). Culturally specific pedagogy in the mathematics classroom. In Routledge eBooks. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781351255837>
- Lindgren, E., Stevenson, M., & Sullivan, K. P. H. (2008a). Supporting the Reflective Language Learner with Computer Keystroke Logging. In IGI Global eBooks (pp. 189–204). <https://doi.org/10.4018/978-1-59904-895-6.ch011>
- Miksza, P., Shaw, J. T., Richerme, L. K., Hash, P. M., Hodges, D. A., & Parker, E. C. (2023). Quantitative descriptive and correlational research. In Oxford University Press eBooks (pp. 241-C12P143). <https://doi.org/10.1093/oso/9780197639757.003.0012>
- Murayama, K., Pekrun, R., Lichtenfeld, S., & Hofe, R. V. (2012). Predicting Long-Term Growth in Students' Mathematics Achievement: The unique contributions of motivation and cognitive Strategies. *Child Development*, 84(4), 1475–1490. <https://doi.org/10.1111/cdev.12036>
- Nathan, S., Haynes, L., Meyer, J., Sumner, J., Hudson-Vitale, C., & McIntosh, L. D. (2021). An analysis of form and function of a research article between and within publishers and journals. *Quantitative Science Studies*, 1–19. https://doi.org/10.1162/qss_a_00135
- Pikulski, J. J., & Chard, D. J. (2005). Fluency: bridge between decoding and reading comprehension. *the Reading Teacher*, 58(6), 510–519. <https://doi.org/10.1598/rt.58.6.2>
- Pouresmaeil, A., & Gholami, J. (2023). The effects of oral incidental focus on form on developing vocabulary knowledge. *TESL-EJ*, 26(4), 1–17. <https://doi.org/10.55593/ej.26104a1>
- Reading habits among students and its effect on academic performance: A study of students of Koforidua Polytechnic. (n.d.). *Library Philosophy and Practice*. https://d1wqtxts1xzle7.cloudfront.net/107086835/viewcontent-libre.pdf?1698850607=&response-content-disposition=inline%3B+filename%3DReading_Habits_Among_Students_and_its_Ef.pdf
- Riehl, C. M. (2021). The interplay of language awareness and bilingual writing abilities in heritage language speakers. *Languages*, 6(2), 94. <https://doi.org/10.3390/languages6020094>
- Russell, M. (2004a). The importance of the affective domain in further education classroom culture. *Research in Post-Compulsory Education*, 9(2), 249–270. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13596740400200178>
- Shakeel, S. (2019). The influence of affective domain on the learning of students at primary level. *Social Science Research Network*. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.3756396>
- Smetana, J. G. (2013). Moral Development. *The Oxford Handbook of Developmental Psychology, Vol. 1: Body and Mind the Oxford Handbook of Developmental Psychology, Vol.*, 831–864. <https://doi.org/10.1093/oxfordhb/9780199958450.013.0029>
- Students Language Awareness in English Classroom of English Education Study Program. (2021). <https://jele.or.id/index.php/jele/index>, ISSN 2597-6850 (Online), 2502-4132. <https://doi.org/10.31004/jele.v6i2.118>
- The Effects of Reading Interest, Reading Purpose, and Reading Maturity on Reading Comprehension of High School Students. (n.d.). *Theses*. https://www.bakeru.edu/images/pdf/SOE/EdD_Theses/Squires_Scot.pdf
- The importance of language awareness. (2008). *diva-portal.org Favicon Diva-portal*. Retrieved January 15, 2024, from <https://www.diva-portal.org/smash/get/diva2:1496995/FULLTEXT01.pdf>
- The use of cognitive domain in questions: The perception of students and lecturers of public universities in Aceh. (2021). *Journal of Language and Linguistic Studies*.
- Thoma, S. J., Scofield, J., May, K. E., Hartin, T. L., & Bui, C. (2021). Judging character: How valence and social domain support character judgments in children and adults. *Cognitive Development*, 58, 101014. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cogdev.2021.101014>
- Tok, E. (2022). Pre-Service Preschool teachers' metacognitive awareness and creative thinking domains. *Shanlax International Journal of Education*, 10(3), 71–78. <https://doi.org/10.34293/education.v10i3.4675>
- Towne, L., Wise, L. L., & Winters, T. M. (2004). Advancing scientific research in education. In National Academies Press eBooks. <https://doi.org/10.17226/11112>
- Typeshare | the digital writing platform. (n.d.). <https://typeshare.co/rebeccaeller/posts/teaching-vocabulary>
- Van Gorp, K., De Costa, P. I., Ponzio, C., Rawal, H., Her, L., & Deng, M. (2023). The emergence of critical multilingual language awareness in teacher education: the role of experience and coursework. *Language Awareness*, 32(4), 662–689.

<https://doi.org/10.1080/09658416.2023.2257601>

Wang, T., & Zhang, H. (2023). Examining the dimensionality of morphological knowledge and morphological awareness and their effects on second language vocabulary knowledge. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 14. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2023.1207854>

Whiteman Air Force Base. (2015, April 10). What is the Social Domain? <https://www.whiteman.af.mil/News/Commentaries/Display/Article/836238/what-is-the-social-domain/>

Wilson, D. V., & Marcin, M. (2022). Building Connections and Critical Language Awareness between Learning Communities Collaborating across Two Distant States. *Languages*, 7(4), 257. <https://doi.org/10.3390/languages7040257>

Xiao-Yan, W. (2021). Cognitive and Affective Learning in English as a Foreign Language/English as a Second Language Instructional-Learning Contexts: Does teacher immediacy matter? *Frontiers in Psychology*, 12. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2021.759784>

Xodabande, I., & Borouhiani, T. (2023). Mobile-assisted focus on forms in English for academic purposes instruction: Investigating the impacts on learning academic words. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 14. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2023.1071555>

Zarfsaz, E., & Yeganehpour, P. (2021). The impact of different context levels on vocabulary learning and retention. *Shanlax International Journal of Education*, 9(4), 24–34. <https://doi.org/10.34293/education.v9i4.4049>

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